

Investigating the impact of galaxies' compact binary hosting probability for gravitational-wave cosmology

G. Perna^{1,2}, S. Mastrogiovanni³, and A. Ricciardone^{4,5,1}

¹ Dipartimento di Fisica e Astronomia “Galileo Galilei”, Università degli Studi di Padova,
Via Marzolo 8, I-35131, Padova, Italy

² INFN, Sezione di Padova,
Via Marzolo 8, I-35131, Padova, Italy

³ INFN, Sezione di Roma, I-00185, Roma, Italy

⁴ Dipartimento di Fisica “Enrico Fermi”, Università di Pisa,
Largo Bruno Pontecorvo 3, Pisa I-56127, Italy

⁵ INFN, Sezione di Pisa,
Largo Bruno Pontecorvo 3, Pisa I-56127, Italy

Received —; accepted —

ABSTRACT

With the advent of future-generation interferometers a huge number of gravitational wave (GW) signals is expected to be measured without an electromagnetic counterpart. Although these signals do not allow a simultaneous measurement of the redshift and the luminosity distance, it is still possible to infer cosmological parameters. In this paper, we focus on the systematic biases that could arise from mismodeling the GW host probability when inferring the Hubble constant (H_0) with GW dark sirens jointly with galaxy catalogues. We discuss the case in which the GW host probability is a function of galaxies' luminosity and redshift as it has been predicted by state-of-the-art compact binary coalescences (CBCs) synthetic catalogues. We show that, in the limiting case in which the analysis is done with a complete galaxy catalog covering a footprint of $\sim 10 \text{ deg}^2$, mismatching the host probability in terms of galaxy's luminosity will introduce a bias on H_0 . In this case, the magnitude of the bias will depend on the distribution of the Large-Scale Structure over the line-of-sight. Instead, in the limit of a complete wide-field of view galaxy catalog and GW events localized at $O(\text{Gpc})$ distance, mismatching the redshift dependence of the GW hosting probability is more likely to introduce a systematic bias.

Key words. gravitational waves – galaxy catalog – cosmology

1. Introduction

The first observation of a gravitational wave (GW) signal in 2015 (Abbott et al. 2016) opened a new complementary way to access information about our Universe, both on the astrophysical and the cosmological sides. On the astrophysical side, after the detection of a further 90 GW events, it has become feasible to infer not only information about the individual sources emitting GWs but also about the mass and spin distributions of the entire population of compact binaries (Abbott et al. 2023b, 2021b). On the cosmological side, GWs can be used to probe the cosmic expansion (Schutz 1986; Holz & Hughes 2005; Dalal et al. 2006) independently to other probes such as Supernovae (Galbany et al. 2023) and the Cosmic Microwave Background (CMB) (Aghanim et al. 2020). This is possible thanks to the fact that GWs directly provide a measurement of the source luminosity distance. Therefore, if provided with a source redshift estimation, GW sources can be used to probe the cosmic expansion. Unfortunately, GWs alone cannot provide a direct measurement of the redshift since it is degenerate with the source masses. A direct estimation of the redshift can be obtained if an electromagnetic counterpart (EM) to the GW source is observed. The EM counterpart could allow the identification of the host galaxy for which it is typically possible to measure the redshift with spectroscopic observations. Indeed, this was the case of the binary neutron star merger GW170817 (Abbott et al. 2017a,b) for

which it has been possible to estimate $H_0 = 70_{-8}^{+12} \text{ km/s/Mpc}$ at 68.3 % credible interval (C.I.). Since then, no additional GW event has been observed with an EM counterpart.

As first argued by Schutz (1986), even in the absence of an electromagnetic counterpart, GW sources can still be employed to measure the cosmic expansion (dark sirens method). There are several techniques proposed in the literature to use dark sirens for cosmology such as the source-frame mass method (Chernoff & Finn 1993; Taylor et al. 2012; Farr 2019; Ezquiaga & Holz 2021; Mastrogiovanni et al. 2021; Mukherjee 2022; Leyde et al. 2022; Ezquiaga & Holz 2022; Karathanasis et al. 2023) and cross-correlations with large-scale structure tracers (Oguri 2016; Mukherjee et al. 2020, 2021; Bera et al. 2020). In this work, we focus on the “galaxy catalogue” technique first proposed by Schutz (1986). This technique consists of assigning a statistical redshift measurement by using the GW source localization and all the galaxies reported in a given survey (Del Pozzo 2012; Chen et al. 2018; Gray et al. 2020; Leandro et al. 2022; Gray et al. 2022; Gair et al. 2023). This is possible since every astrophysical GW event is expected to be hosted in a galaxy¹. Although the galaxy catalogue method is less precise inferring H_0 than a single event with EM counterpart, it is expected to play a relevant role

¹ Unless it is sourced by primordial black holes formed at early Universe ages (Sasaki et al. 2018) or it results from the merger of binaries with large kick velocities (Gerosa & Moore 2016). Both these types of events are expected to be very rare.

for GW cosmology given the number of dark sirens detections as demonstrated by its several current applications (Fishbach et al. 2019; Soares-Santos et al. 2019; Abbott et al. 2021a; Palmese et al. 2020, 2023; Abbott et al. 2023a; Finke et al. 2021; Mastrogiovanni et al. 2023; Borghi et al. 2024). Furthermore, with the advent of future generation interferometers such as LISA (Aulclair et al. 2023), Cosmic Explorer (CE) (Evans et al. 2021) and Einstein Telescope (ET) (Maggiore et al. 2020; Branchesi et al. 2023), a much higher number of GW signals are expected to be detected, further emphasizing the importance of such analysis.

A central topic of the galaxy catalogue method is how to describe for each galaxy the probability of hosting a GW event. The simplest choice might be to assume that every galaxy has an equal probability to host a GW event, even though this is not a physically motivated assumption as we observe that the overall Star Formation Rate (SFR), and hence the compact objects produced, correlates with several galactic properties (Madau & Dickinson 2014). Furthermore, as shown in Hanselman et al. (2025), assuming equal host probabilities can lead to biases in the estimated value of H_0 . As such, current analyses include a hosting probability based on the intrinsic luminosity of the galaxies, namely the brighter the galaxy, the more likely it is to host a GW event (some recent predictions for host galaxies properties are discussed in Vijaykumar et al. (2024); Artale et al. (2020)). It has been shown in Gray et al. (2020) that luminosity weights can boost the H_0 precision, however, there is no current study about the systematics on H_0 that these assumptions can introduce.

In this work, we study in detail how modelling the GW host probability can introduce systematics when inferring H_0 . We build our study on the simulation approach presented in Gair et al. (2023). Starting from a simulated Universe (MICEcat) (Crocce et al. 2015), we populate GW events in each galaxy following a hosting probability model obtained from synthetic catalogues of CBCs (Artale et al. 2020). We then use different selection criteria for the GW events and different GW hosting probability models to study the possible presence of biases for the H_0 inference. This work is organized as follows. We start in Section 2 describing the statistical framework we consider in our analysis. In Section 3 we present the simulated Universe considered for the simulation we argue about the GW data generation technique. Finally in Section 4 we discuss the results of our analysis, while in Section 5 we report our conclusions.

2. Statistical framework

In this section we describe the statistical framework employed for our study.

2.1. General prescription for H_0 inference

The posterior on H_0 inferred from the detection of N_{GW} events from a collection of data $\{x\}$, can be obtained using the Bayes theorem (e.g. (Sivia & Skilling 2006))

$$p(H_0|\{x\}) \propto \mathcal{L}(\{x|H_0)p(H_0), \quad (1)$$

where $p(H_0)$ is a prior and $\mathcal{L}(\{x|H_0)$ the likelihood. The likelihood describes the GW detection as an inhomogeneous Poisson process in the presence of selection biases (Mandel et al. 2019; Vitale et al. 2020). Neglecting the information on the binary masses, for the galaxy catalogue technique the likelihood

can be written as (Gair et al. 2023)

$$\mathcal{L}(\{x|H_0) \propto e^{-N_{\text{exp}}(H_0)} [N_{\text{exp}}(H_0)]^{N_{\text{GW}}} \times \prod_i^{N_{\text{GW}}} \frac{\int dz d\Omega \mathcal{L}_{\text{GW}}(x_i|d_L(z, H_0), \Omega) p_{\text{CBC}}(z, \Omega)}{\int dz d\Omega P_{\text{det}}^{\text{GW}}(z, H_0, \Omega) p_{\text{CBC}}(z, \Omega)}, \quad (2)$$

where N_{exp} is the expected number of GW detections, z the source redshift, Ω the sky location, $\mathcal{L}_{\text{GW}}(x_i|d_L(z, H_0), \Omega)$ the GW likelihood (i.e. how well we can measure the luminosity distance and sky position), $P_{\text{det}}^{\text{GW}}(z, H_0, \Omega)$ the GW detection probability and $p_{\text{CBC}}(z, \Omega)$ the probability of finding CBC at redshift z and sky position Ω . By assuming that the GW likelihood is reasonably constant in a given sky area Ω_{loc} , and that the detection probability does not vary in this sky area, i.e. $P_{\text{det}}^{\text{GW}}(z, H_0, \Omega) \approx P_{\text{det}}^{\text{GW}}(z, H_0)$, Eq. 2 can be rewritten dropping the sky-localization dependency and defining $p_{\text{CBC,loc}}(z) \propto p_{\text{CBC}}(z, \Omega_{\text{loc}})$. In the remainder of the paper we will refer to $p_{\text{CBC,loc}}(z)$ with simply $p_{\text{CBC}}(z)$ for brevity reasons. Later in this section, we will explain how to construct $p_{\text{CBC}}(z)$ taking into account a non-trivial GW hosting probability. Eq. 2 can be marginalized analytically on N_{exp} (Fishbach et al. 2018) by assuming a flat-in-log prior thus obtaining the identity

$$\mathcal{L}(\{x|H_0) \propto \prod_i^{N_{\text{GW}}} \frac{\int dz \mathcal{L}_{\text{GW}}(x_i|d_L(z, H_0)) p_{\text{CBC}}(z)}{\int dz P_{\text{det}}^{\text{GW}}(z, H_0) p_{\text{CBC}}(z)}. \quad (3)$$

For this work, we model the GW likelihood using the same toy model of Gair et al. (2023),

$$\mathcal{L}_{\text{GW}}(\hat{d}_L^i|d_L(z, H_0)) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2\pi} A d_L(z, H_0)} e^{-\frac{(\hat{d}_L^i - d_L(z, H_0))^2}{2A^2 d_L^2(z, H_0)}} \quad (4)$$

where we identify the data chunk x_i as an ‘‘observed’’ luminosity distance \hat{d}_L^i on which we apply a selection cut. In Eq. above, $A = 0.2$ is chosen to mimic a typical error budget on the luminosity distance of 20%. As argued in Gair et al. (2023), it is important to apply the selection cut strictly on the observed luminosity distance to avoid introducing a systematic bias due to the incongruent statistical model, see (Essick & Fishbach 2024) for a general detailed discussion about physical and unphysical statistical models. The detection probability is defined for each ‘‘true’’ d_L by integrating over all the observable data sets \hat{d}_L . Following (Gair et al. 2023), we assume that GWs are detected if their observed luminosity distance is lower than a certain horizon \hat{d}_L^{thr} , namely

$$P_{\text{det}}^{\text{GW}}(d_L) = \int_{-\infty}^{\hat{d}_L^{\text{thr}}} \mathcal{L}_{\text{GW}}(\hat{d}_L|d_L(z, H_0)) d\hat{d}_L = \frac{1}{2} \left[1 + \text{erf} \left(\frac{d_L(z, H_0) - \hat{d}_L^{\text{thr}}}{\sqrt{2} A d_L(z, H_0)} \right) \right]. \quad (5)$$

This simple prescription of the GW detection horizon is nearly equivalent to considering a selection criteria based on the signal-to-noise ratio (SNR). In fact, for GW sources, the SNR is proportional to the inverse of the luminosity distance. Before proceeding to the construction of a galaxy-informed $p_{\text{CBC}}(z)$, let us clarify that this type of statistical framework does not apply to real data. In a realistic scenario, the GW detection probability will depend on other parameters such as the detector masses of the GW signals. Moreover, we are not able to define a model that approximates x_i with ‘‘observed’’ quantities. As such, real data analysis techniques such as Mastrogiovanni et al. (2024),

146 use parameter estimation samples generated from data x_i in syn- 190
147 ergy with an injection campaign to correct selection biases. For 191
148 all these reasons, the computational complexity does not allow
149 for an extensive and straightforward Monte Carlo study on how
150 the GW hosting probability translates to a H_0 bias.

151 2.2. Building the compact binary coalescence probability

152 We model $p_{\text{CBC}}(z)$ following Mastrogiovanni et al. (2023); Gray
153 et al. (2023); Borghi et al. (2024)

$$p_{\text{CBC}}(z) = \frac{\int dM f_{\text{rate}}(z, M) p_{\text{cat}}(z, M)}{\int dM dz f_{\text{rate}}(z, M) p_{\text{cat}}(z, M)}, \quad (6)$$

154 where f_{rate} is a function that parametrizes the probability that
155 a galaxy with redshift z and absolute magnitude M is likely to
156 host a GW signal, while $p_{\text{cat}}(z, M)$ is the distribution of galaxies
157 in terms of redshift and absolute magnitude in a given sky pixel².
158 This parametrization of $p_{\text{CBC}}(z)$ is an extension to the one pro-
159 vided in Gair et al. (2023) that considered only a dependence
160 of the CBC rate from the galaxy redshift. Moreover, this pa-
161 rameterization requires that the redshift and apparent magnitude
162 (from which the absolute magnitude is computed) be accurately
163 measured, otherwise a prior term on the distribution of absolute
164 magnitudes in the Universe should be included. In principle, we
165 could extend Eq. 6 to include any galactic property. Here we just
166 focus on absolute magnitude (i.e., intrinsic luminosity) as it is
167 the usual galactic property used to model the GW hosting prob-
168 ability. Before describing the modelization of $f_{\text{rate}}(z, M)$, let us
169 briefly comment on Eq. 6. If all the galaxies are equally likely to
170 host a GW source, then $f_{\text{rate}}(z, M)$ is constant and

$$p_{\text{CBC}}(z) = \int dM p_{\text{cat}}(z, M) = p_{\text{cat}}(z). \quad (7)$$

171 In other words, the distribution of possible CBC hosts will con-
172 coincide to the distribution of galaxies over the line-of-sight. How-
173 ever, if $f_{\text{rate}}(z, M)$ is not uniform, this will not be the case.

174 We model the rate function using a model similar to Mastro-
175 giovanni et al. (2023), namely

$$f_{\text{rate}}(z, M) = \psi_{\text{CBC}}(z) 10^{-0.4 \epsilon (M - M_*)}, \quad (8)$$

176 where M_* is the Schechter function knee value for the galaxies'
177 luminosity distribution. $\psi_{\text{CBC}}(z)$ is a function that we compute
178 numerically to parameterize the CBC merger rate as a function
179 of redshift (see Sec. 3) and

$$10^{-0.4 \epsilon (M - M_*)} = \left(\frac{L}{L_*} \right)^\epsilon, \quad (9)$$

180 a term that introduces a power-law dependence for the host prob-
181 ability, which depends on the galaxies' intrinsic luminosity. This
182 simple parametrization is inspired from Artale et al. (2020),
183 where it is argued, starting from synthetic simulations of CBCs,
184 that the CBC merger rate has a dependence on the galaxies' red-
185 shift (due to the different star formation rate and time delays) and
186 galaxies' luminosity (due to the total stellar mass).

187 Finally, let us discuss how we practically calculate and em-
188 ploy $p_{\text{cat}}(z, M)$. Assuming that we are provided with a complete
189 galaxy catalog reporting N_{gal} galaxies with a collection redshifts

$\{z_g^i\}$ and apparent magnitudes $\{\hat{m}_g^i\}$, then following Gair et al. 190
(2023); Mastrogiovanni et al. (2023) we have 191

$$p_{\text{cat}}(z, M) \approx \frac{1}{N_{\text{gal}}} \sum_i^{N_{\text{gal}}} p(z|z_g^i) p(m(M, H_0, z)|\hat{m}_{g,*}^i), \quad (10)$$

192 where the terms indicated with $p(\cdot)$ are the single posteriors on 192
each galaxy true redshift and apparent magnitude. In order to 193
better focus on the systematics introduced by the modelling of 194
 $f_{\text{rate}}(z, M)$, we assume that we have perfectly measured redshift 195
and apparent magnitude of the galaxies. These are reasonable 196
assumptions for galaxies whose redshift is estimated with spec- 197
troscopic observations. When the errors on the galaxies' redshift 198
and apparent magnitude are small, 199

$$p_{\text{cat}}(z, M) \approx \frac{1}{N_{\text{gal}}} \sum_i^{N_{\text{gal}}} \delta(z - z_g^i) \delta(m(M, H_0, z) - \hat{m}_{g,*}^i). \quad (11)$$

199 In practice, we never compute $p_{\text{cat}}(z, M)$. In fact by substituting 200
Eq. 11 in Eq. 6 and later considering the hierarchical likelihood 201
in Eq. 3, with the GW likelihood model in Eq. 4, it is possible to 202
show that 203

$$\mathcal{L}(\{x_i\}|H_0) \propto \prod_i^{N_{\text{GW}}} \frac{\sum_i^{N_{\text{gal}}} \mathcal{L}_{\text{GW}}(\hat{d}_L^i | d_L(z_g^i, H_0)) f_{\text{rate}}(z_g^i, M(\hat{m}_g^i, H_0, z_g^i))}{\sum_i^{N_{\text{gal}}} P_{\text{det}}^{\text{GW}}(z_g^i, H_0) f_{\text{rate}}(z_g^i, M(\hat{m}_g^i, H_0, z_g^i))}. \quad (12)$$

204 3. Simulation setup and catalogs description

205 We provide an overview of the data products and simulation pro-
206 cedures used for this study. In Sec. 3.1 we describe the MICECat
207 catalogue, a simulated Universe used to assign the GW galaxy
208 hosts. In Sec. 3.2 we discuss the procedure to generate the GW
209 signals starting from the galaxies list and in Sec. 3.3 we discuss
210 some of the features of the GW catalogues generated from the
211 simulation.

212 3.1. Description of MICEcat and GW host probability model

213 In this work, we use MICECat, a galaxy catalogue generated
214 from the MICE Grand Challenge lightcone simulation (Fosalba
215 et al. 2015a; Crocce et al. 2015; Fosalba et al. 2015b; Carretero
216 et al. 2015; Hoffmann et al. 2015), i.e. a full N-body simulation
217 of the Universe containing about 70 billion dark matter particles.
218 MICEcat has been generated using the following set of cosmo-
219 logical parameters, $\Omega_m = 0.25$, $\sigma_8 = 0.8$, $n_s = 0.95$, $\Omega_b = 0.044$,
220 $\Omega_\Lambda = 0.75$, $h = 0.7$ for a fiducial Λ CDM model. The lightcone
221 simulation has been performed in the redshift range $0 < z < 1.4$,
222 and using a hybrid halo occupation distribution and halo abun-
223 dance matching prescriptions to populate friends-of-friends dark
224 matter halos, whose masses are greater than $2.2 \cdot 10^{11} M_\odot/h$
225 (Crocce et al. 2015). MICEcat reports the true redshift and the
226 true absolute magnitude M_r in the infrared band (r-band) for all
227 the galaxies. The catalogue covers only 1/8 of the full sky in the
228 redshift range and is complete up to redshift 1.4.

229 We model the GW host probability for each event using the
230 parametrization for f_{rate} in Eq. 8. The redshift dependence of the
231 CBC rate function is obtained with the procedure used in Bel-
232 lomo et al. (2022). We start from the phenomenological expres-
233 sion provided by Madau-Dickinson for star formation rate (SFR)
234 in Madau & Dickinson (2014),

$$\mathcal{R}_{\text{SFR}}(z) \propto \frac{(1+z)^{\lambda_1}}{1 + \left(\frac{1+z}{\lambda_2}\right)^{\lambda_1 + \lambda_2}}, \quad (13)$$

² Let us remind the reader that this is a consequence of the fact that we have assumed the GW likelihood uniform in a given sky area.

235 with $\lambda_1 = 2.7$, $\lambda_2 = 2.9$, valid for the redshift range $0 \leq x \leq 8$.
236 We assume that there is no cosmologically significant time delay
237 between the formation of the stellar progenitor and the compact
238 object, this is motivated since compact objects are born from
239 massive stars that are expected to live tens of Myrs. We then, use
240 a simple model to account for the time delay in compact object
241 formation and merger, the merger rate can be written as

$$\psi_{\text{CBC}}(z) \propto \int_{t_{\text{d,min}}}^{t(z)} \mathcal{R}_{\text{SFR}}(z(t_d)) p(t_d) dt_d, \quad (14)$$

242 with $t_{\text{d,min}} = 50 \text{ Myr}^3$ and $p(t_d) \propto t_d^{-1}$. We verify that, after
243 this step, the redshift dependence of the merger rate goes like
244 $(1+z)^{1.82}$ consistently with current observations (Abbott et al.
245 2021c). We find that a good fit for the merger rate, after account-
246 ing for the time delay, yields

$$\psi_{\text{CBC}}(z) \propto \frac{1}{1+z} \frac{(1+z)^{1.82}}{1 + (\frac{z}{2})^{3.82}}, \quad (15)$$

247 where the $1/(1+z)$ factor is introduced to account for the time
248 dilation between the source frame and the detector frame due to
249 the expansion of the Universe. We also add that the merger rate
250 model that we implement is set to 0 for $z > 1.4$ as MICEcat is
251 truncated at $z = 1.4$. This hard cut can create a bias on H_0 if
252 not accounted for and if correctly accounted can also improve
253 the precision of the H_0 measure as the CBC merger rate dis-
254 plays a sharp redshift scale that can be used for the inference.
255 However, this is not our case as even for our furthest detection
256 threshold (4250 Mpc), the fraction of detectable events above
257 redshift 1.4 is estimated to be $\lesssim 2\%$ for an extreme value of
258 $H_0 = 120 \text{ km s}^{-1} \text{ Mpc}^{-1}$.

259 The CBC rate dependence from the galaxies' intrinsic lumi-
260 nosities has not yet been measured. Therefore, we use a model
261 calibrated on the astrophysical simulations of CBC formation
262 performed in Artale et al. (2020). In this study, the authors pro-
263 vide a fit to the GW hosting probability as a function of the
264 galaxy luminosity in the K-band (which is expected to be a rea-
265 sonable tracer of the galaxy's total stellar mass). In Fig. 1, we
266 report the GW host probability as a function of absolute mag-
267 nitude in the K-band, M_K provided by Artale et al. (2020). As
268 it can be seen from the plot, the GW host probability is not ex-
269 pected to strongly evolve for redshifts ≤ 2 , a limit that is above
270 the GW events that we consider detectable in our simulation (see
271 later). Therefore, for our case study, we assume that the GW host
272 probability in terms of galaxy luminosity does not evolve with
273 redshift. The best-fitting ϵ (c.f. Eq. 6) in Fig. 1 is 2.25, that cor-
274 responds to GW hosting probability in terms of luminosity

$$p(L) \propto L^{\frac{9}{4}}, \quad (16)$$

275 and we show in Fig. 1 in comparison with the numerical values
276 provided by Artale et al. (2020). Hence, under the approxima-
277 tions done so far, the final merger rate model we consider results
278

$$f_{\text{rate}}(z, L) \propto L^{\frac{9}{4}} \frac{1}{1+z} \frac{(1+z)^{1.82}}{1 + (\frac{z}{2})^{3.82}}. \quad (17)$$

279 We warrant that typically the star formation rate at low red-
280 shift is not separable into two independent terms (Behroozi et al.
281 2013), namely $f_{\text{SFR}}(z, L) \neq f_{\text{SFR}}(z) f_{\text{SFR}}(L)$. As a consequence,

³ See Bellomo et al. (2022) for additional details on the integration boundaries.

Fig. 1. The plot reports the GW host probability as a function of the galaxies's absolute magnitude in the K-band. Different lines indicate the host probability at different redshifts. The GW host probability has been extracted from Artale et al. (2020).

282 if the CBC merger rate perfectly tracks the star formation rate,
283 our model in Eq. 17 should be revisited as additional biases
284 on H_0 could be introduced by the z, L interplay. However, cur-
285 rently, the CBC merger rate as a function of z and L is not
286 measured from data and the simulations of Artale et al. (2020)
287 predicts that the GW host probability can be approximated as
288 $f_{\text{CBC}}(z, L) \approx f_{\text{CBC}}(z) f_{\text{CBC}}(L)$, also at low redshift. This can also
289 be appreciated in Fig. 1, obtained from Artale et al. (2020),
290 where we can see that the GW host probability as a function of
291 M_K is different only for sources at $z \gtrsim 5$.

3.2. Simulation of the GW catalogue

292 In Fig. 2 we summarize the steps taken to obtain the GW cata-
293 logue from MICEcat.

294 As argued in Sec. 2, we perform our study by considering
295 several sky localization areas for the GW events, hence the first
296 step of the simulation is to filter all the galaxies reported by
297 MICEcat in a given sky location. To do so, we use the python
298 package healpy (Zonca et al. 2019) to divide the sky in equal-
299 sized pixels with the same sky area and then select all the galax-
300 ies falling in each of these line-of-sights (LOSs) considered. For
301 this study, we consider sky localization areas of 1 deg^2 , 10 deg^2
302 and 100 deg^2 to mimic the typical sky localizations of a net-
303 work made by 3 GW detectors (Kagra Collaboration & VIRGO
304 Collaboration 2018). When dealing with GW events localized
305 within 1 deg^2 and 10 deg^2 , we consider 100 pixels randomly dis-
306 tributed in the sky octant, while in the case that we are working
307 with pixels of 100 deg^2 we subdivide the sky into 60 pixels.

308 After a LOS is selected, we apply a subsampling of all the
309 galaxies reported by MICEcat. The resampling procedure is ap-
310 plied to speedup the computation of the hierarchical likelihood
311 in Eq. 12, this is required due to the extensive number of runs
312

Fig. 2. Flowchart of the process to simulate GW events from MICEcat.

Fig. 3. The histograms report the distribution of detected GW events, for different thresholds on the observed luminosity distance and number of detected events. The sky area considered corresponds to a sky-localization of 1 deg^2 as an example.

313 that we have performed. We have verified that about ~ 3000
 314 galaxies for each line of sight are enough to preserve the large-
 315 scale structures in redshift from which the Hubble constant is
 316 estimated, see App. A for more details. After the galaxies have
 317 been subsampled, we calculate for each of them a relative weight
 318 using Eq. 6 to host a GW events.

319 Using the calculated weights, we extract a galaxy as an host
 320 of the GW event and we compute its luminosity distance d_L us-
 321 ing the true cosmological model. Then we extract a value of
 322 the “observed” luminosity distance \hat{d}_L using the GW likelihood
 323 model in Eq. 4. If the observed luminosity distance is lower
 324 than a detection threshold \hat{d}_L^{thr} , then we consider the signal as
 325 detected.

326 We iterate the procedure described in this section until the
 327 desired number of GW sources is obtained.

328 3.3. Properties of the GW catalogs

329 Fig. 3 shows the distributions of the detected GW events for
 330 the three detection thresholds. The first property of the detected
 331 population is that the true redshift (luminosity distance) of the
 332 sources can extend beyond \hat{d}_L^{thr} . This is because the GW like-
 333 likelihood model can introduce noise fluctuations that make the
 334 signals detectable. From Fig. 3, we can also observe that a
 335 $\hat{d}_L^{\text{thr}} = 500 \text{ Mpc}$ would result in a population of GW events typ-
 336 ically detected within redshift 0.2, $\hat{d}_L^{\text{thr}} = 1550 \text{ Mpc}$ within red-
 337 shift 0.4 and $\hat{d}_L^{\text{thr}} = 4250 \text{ Mpc}$ within redshift 1. None of our
 338 simulations contains GW sources from galaxies close $z \approx 1.4$,
 339 which is the cut used to generate MICEcat. As such, our studies
 340 do not need to account for the presence of this hard cut in the
 341 galaxy distributions.

342 To quantify better how GWs detected at various distances
 343 interact with the construction of the galaxies' overdensity in the

line-of-sight, we compute the single event likelihood

344

$$\mathcal{L}(\hat{d}_L | H_0^{\text{MICE}}) \equiv \frac{\sum_i^{N_{\text{gal}}} \mathcal{L}_{\text{GW}}(\hat{d}_L | d_L(z_g^i, H_0)) f_{\text{rate}}(z_g^i, M(\hat{m}_g^i, H_0, z_g^i))}{\sum_i^{N_{\text{gal}}} P_{\text{det}}^{\text{GW}}(z_g^i, H_0) f_{\text{rate}}(z_g^i, M(\hat{m}_g^i, H_0, z_g^i))}. \quad (18)$$

345 as a function of the observed distance \hat{d}_L and conditioned on
 346 the true value of H_0^{MICE} used to generate MICEcat. The single-
 347 likelihood profile can be used to understand how sensitive is the
 348 analyses to changes in the prescription of f_{rate} . If the likelihood
 349 profile as a function of \hat{d}_L is not modified as the prescription
 350 of f_{rate} changes, then the H_0 posterior is not expected to differ.
 351 We note that what impacts on the estimation of H_0 are changes
 352 in the trend of the likelihood and not its overall normalization
 353 factor. In Fig. 4 we show this estimator calculated for three dif-
 354 ferent LOSs areas. As we can see from the plots, GW events
 355 observed at low distances for small sky areas display large like-
 356 likelihood changes when the galaxy's luminosity is included in the
 357 localization volume, a change in the GW host probability would system-
 358 atically prefer few galaxies, while if many galaxies are included
 359 there is no such preference. Instead, a change of prescription of
 360 f_{rate} as a function of redshift does not affect the single-likelihood
 361 as this weight at low redshift is equal for all the galaxies. At
 362 higher distances (redshift), the redshift weight in f_{rate} causes a
 363 more negligible change in the trend of the single event likeli-
 364 hood.
 365

366 4. Forecasting systematics on the H_0 inference

366

367 In this section, we present an extensive study on the systematics
 368 that could be introduced in the estimation of H_0 when mismodel-
 369 ing the GW host probability, namely the rate function f_{rate} . To do

Fig. 4. Single-likelihood estimator (c.f. Eq. 18) on the vertical axes as a function of the observed luminosity distance on the horizontal axis. The top, middle and bottom panels are generated assuming that the GW event is localized in a 1 deg², 10 deg² and 100 deg² sky area. The different lines are generated assuming the four prescriptions of f_{rate} used in this work. The figure has been generated assuming a $\hat{d}_L^{\text{thr}} = 500$ Mpc (we note that such a choice just acts as an overall normalization constant).

so, we simulate 100, 200 and 500 GW detections from MICEcat using the fiducial model for f_{rate} in Eq. 8 and we then perform the inference using 4 different models for f_{rate} . The first is the correct one and accounts for both redshift and absolute magnitude dependence, the second neglects the absolute magnitude, the third the redshift dependence and the fourth both the absolute magnitude and redshift. In estimating the H_0 we use a uniform prior in the range [40, 120] km s⁻¹Mpc⁻¹.

For each of these cases, we build probability-probability (PP) plots (e.g., Wilk & Gnanadesikan (1968)) for the H_0 posterior. PP plots are built by repeating each simulation 100 times, each time drawing a value for H_0 in the prior range [40, 120] km s⁻¹Mpc⁻¹. For each posterior obtained, we compute at which credible interval \mathcal{I} the true value of H_0^{inj} is found, namely

$$\mathcal{I}_i = \int_{40 \text{ km s}^{-1} \text{ Mpc}^{-1}}^{H_0^{\text{inj}, i}} p(H_0 | \{x\}) dH_0. \quad (19)$$

If no bias is present, the distribution of the \mathcal{I}_i is expected to be uniform in the range [0,1] and its cumulative (the PP-plot) is expected to be a bisector in the range [0,1].

4.1. Case 1: All GW sources are observed in the same line-of-sight

We first start by discussing a simple case in which all the GW detections are obtained from the same LOS. In this limiting case, the distribution of galaxies, from the GW point of view, will strongly deviate from a uniform in comoving volume distribution. This is due to the fact we are observing GWs from the same LOS that contains always the same anisotropies in the redshift and luminosity distribution of galaxies. Thus we expect that systematically mismatching f_{rate} for the same set of galaxies might introduce a systematic bias on the H_0 estimation.

In Fig. 5 we show the PP plots for the various cases that we simulated using a sky localization area of 10 deg². In all the cases, we obtain that when f_{rate} is modelled correctly, the inference does not show any significant bias, as expected. However, if we consider a detection horizon ≤ 1550 Mpc, i.e. we are observing GW events at small distances, we obtain that mismodelling f_{rate} can introduce a significant bias. In particular, we found that if galaxy luminosities are neglected, then the H_0 posterior will typically display a bias towards higher values of H_0 and this effect depends on the galaxy distribution along the LOS considered. In fact, from the plots in Fig. 5, we can also observe that this is the dominant source of the bias, even if the redshift dependence of f_{rate} is neglected. The magnitude of the H_0 bias increases as more GW events are used for the inference as expected for a systematic bias stacking on each of the GW events analyzed. If we consider $\hat{d}_L^{\text{thr}} = 4250$ Mpc, we find that mismodelling f_{rate} does not introduce any significant bias. We verified that the results obtained for 10 deg² are also valid for 1 deg², while for 100 deg² the bias results weakened since, when considering large volumes, the local anisotropy tends to be averaged out.

The results presented in the previous paragraph can be explained as follows. On one hand, when $\hat{d}_L^{\text{thr}} < 1550$ Mpc, we are typically dealing with close-by GW events whose luminosity distance uncertainties are “small”⁴. As a consequence, they include in their localization volume galaxies distributed in a narrow redshift space but can show some significant anisotropies in terms of luminosity distribution. Therefore, mismatching the dependence of f_{rate} from the galaxies’ luminosity introduces a strong bias for the inference while the effect of mismatching the redshift dependence is small. On the other hand, if we have a detection threshold $\hat{d}_L^{\text{thr}} = 4250$ Mpc, most of the GW events will be located at high distances and will have a large localization volume. As a consequence, they will include galaxies over a wide redshift range but as the redshift range is large, we do not expect to see any significant anisotropy in their distribution in terms of luminosity. It follows that in this case, mismodelling the redshift dependence on f_{rate} is more important than mismodelling luminosity dependence. Fig. 4 corroborates the above discussion, which shows that the single-event likelihood is different at low redshift when mismatching the luminosity weight and at high redshift when mismatching the redshift dependence.

The behavior of H_0 is directly linked to the type of mismodelling that we are doing on f_{rate} . Remembering that $H_0 \propto z/d_L$, when a bias is introduced by a wrong modelling of the redshift dependence, we systematically prefer to set GW hosts at lower redshift compared to their true distribution. This will result in a bias towards lower H_0 values (hinted also by the curves in Fig. 5). When we neglect the intrinsic luminosity dependence

⁴ remember that in our model the typical luminosity distance uncertainties are of the order of 20% the luminosity distance

Fig. 5. PP Plots corresponding to a single line of sight covering a sky-area of 10 deg^2 . The rows correspond to the three different thresholds in luminosity distance, the columns to different number of detected GW events N_{GW} .

447 of f_{rate} , we are more likely to assign GW events to faint galaxies
 448 and for this particular LOS translates to a high H_0 bias. To provide
 449 a more qualitative picture of the biases, we show in Fig. 6
 450 the reconstructed posterior for $d_L^{\text{thr}} = 1550 \text{ Mpc}$ and 200 detected
 451 GWs and with a sky area of 10 deg^2 , where the true value of H_0
 452 has been set to $70 \text{ km s}^{-1} \text{ Mpc}^{-1}$. As it can be seen from the
 453 plot, the H_0 posterior is sensitive to the models of f_{rate} . Although
 454 for this particular case, the statistical errors are sufficiently large
 455 to include the true value of H_0 , the overall statistical framework
 456 suffers from systematic biases as demonstrated by the PP plots.

457 4.2. Case 2: GWs from all the sky directions

458 We now repeat the same studies of the section above by randomizing
 459 the LOS from which each GW event is observed. This procedure is
 460 equivalent to assuming that the GW distribution is isotropic in our
 461 Universe. In this case, we would expect the average distribution of
 462 galaxies in redshifts over all the LOSs to be reasonably uniform in
 463 comoving volume and thus, any local anisotropy present in the
 464 luminosity distribution should be averaged out. In other words, we
 465 would expect that when not ac-

counting for the galaxies' luminosity in f_{rate} , the systematic introduced
 on H_0 will be sometimes to the right and sometimes to the left, thus
 resulting in no bias. When we consider GW events detected at distances
 of $O(\text{Gpc})$, mismatching the redshift dependence leads to a further
 systematic bias, shifting the posterior towards lower values of H_0 .
 As explained in the previous section, when the redshift range considered
 is large, mismodelling the redshift dependence translates in preferring
 nearer galaxies as GW hosts, hence providing a shift of the posterior
 to the left.

Fig. 7 shows the PP plots for a sky area of 10 deg^2 . Also in this
 case, we observe similar behaviours to the ones observed in the previous
 section: if the CBC rate function as a function of redshift is mismatched,
 this will result in a bias when considering GW events detected at higher
 distances. Differently to the single-LOS case, when the intrinsic galaxy
 luminosity is mismatched, we obtain the posterior on H_0 that is typically
 unbiased, even for close-by and well-localized GW events. This is
 consistent with the fact that by marginalizing over different LOSs,
 galaxies' clustering properties tend to follow a uniform comoving volume
 distribution that is unaffected by the actual galactic properties. We
 provide a qualitative picture in Fig 8, where we show the reconstructed
 posterior for $d_L^{\text{thr}} = 4250 \text{ Mpc}$ and 500 detected

Fig. 6. Posterior obtained fixing H_0 to $70 \text{ km s}^{-1} \text{ Mpc}^{-1}$, $\hat{d}_L^{\text{thr}} = 1550$ Mpc and the 200 detected GWs, for the same line of sight and a sky area of 10 deg^2 .

488 GWs and with a sky area of 10 deg^2 , where the true value of H_0
489 has been set to $70 \text{ km s}^{-1} \text{ Mpc}^{-1}$.

490 5. Conclusions

491 In this work, we have performed a further systematic study on
492 the bias that can be introduced on the inference of H_0 for dark
493 sirens cosmology with galaxy catalogs. We performed extensive
494 end-to-end simulations to infer H_0 from GW standard sirens
495 starting from MICEcat, a simulated universe reproducing the
496 large-scale structures properties of our Universe.

497 Assuming the galaxy catalogue to be complete and with a
498 set of simplified assumptions for the GW detection probability
499 and GW localization, we have shown that mismodelling of the
500 CBC host probability, namely f_{rate} , can introduce relevant bi-
501 ases when estimating H_0 . We have found that mismatching the
502 f_{rate} dependence as a function of redshift will most likely intro-
503 duce a systematic shift at low H_0 when dealing with hundreds
504 of GW detections detected at luminosity distances higher than
505 2 Gpc . We have also found that mismatching f_{rate} as a function
506 of the galaxy's luminosities might introduce a systematic bias
507 on H_0 when dealing with multiple events from the same LOS
508 detected at very close distances. However, we have shown for
509 the first time that when dealing with GW events from different
510 LOSs, even close ones, mismatching the galaxy luminosity depen-
511 dence in f_{rate} is not expected to bring significant bias on H_0 .

512 The results presented in this paper are also scalable to other
513 GW detector networks. If we assume that the luminosity distance
514 errors do not strongly change with the SNR⁵, then the luminos-
515 ity distance detection thresholds could be rephrased in terms of
516 SNR detection thresholds. Thus working with luminosity dis-
517 tance threshold would implicitly mean working with standard

⁵ This is a reasonable assumption if we assume that the luminos-
ity distance inclination degeneracy dominates the GW error budget
(Chassande-Mottin et al. 2019).

518 sirens selecting according to an SNR cut that depends on the de-
519 tector network. As an example, a binary black hole binary at 500
520 Mpc with current GW detectors would enter the analysis with a
521 SNR cut of $\gtrsim 40$, while for future generation detectors would
522 enter the analysis for an SNR cut $\gtrsim 10^3$.

523 We warrant that these results are valid with some caveats.
524 We assumed that more than 100 GW events were used for the
525 H_0 inference. In the case of a low number of GW detections (i.e.
526 few localized standard sirens with very high SNR), we expect
527 that assumptions on the host galaxy properties might introduce
528 a systematic bias of H_0 as on average the LSSs seen by the GW
529 events are not uniform in comoving volume. In other words, a
530 low number of highly localized GW sources would mimic the
531 behaviour observed for the case of 100 well-localized sources
532 drawn from the same LOS.

533 On one hand, our results were generated assuming a com-
534 plete galaxy catalog in terms of CBC hosts. On the other hand,
535 for populations of GW sources at high redshift, where current
536 catalogs are expected to be incomplete, a bias will most likely
537 be introduced by a mismodelling of the CBC merger rate as a
538 function of redshift. The CBC merger rate as function of redshift
539 needs to be also modelled for the completeness correction, with
540 the same exact parametrization of $f_{\text{rate}}(z)$. Therefore, we expect
541 that for this case our results will remain unchanged even if we
542 include the completeness correction. At the same time, we also
543 expect that for close-by GW events, our results will not vary as
544 the galaxy catalog would be nearly complete, of course, the level
545 of completeness will strongly depend on the apparent magnitude
546 sensitivities. It is currently unknown how mismatching the com-
547 pleteness correction would result in a systematic bias for cata-
548 logs that are not 100% complete or incomplete. We leave this
549 analysis for more dedicated studies as simulating galaxy cata-
550 logs incompleteness involves several survey-specific issues such
551 as modelling of the Schechter function as also dependent on red-
552 shift, the definition of realistic apparent magnitude cuts, color
553 corrections etc.

554 *Acknowledgements.* CloudVeneto is acknowledged for the use of computing
555 and storage facilities. A.R. thanks Steven N. Shore for valuable comments on
556 the draft and M. Cignoni for discussions. AR acknowledges financial support
557 from the Italian Ministry of University and Research (MUR) for the PRIN grant
558 METE under contract no. 2020KB33TP and from the Supporting TAlent in Re-
559 Search@University of Padova (STARS@UNIPD) for the project ‘‘Constraining
560 Cosmology and Astrophysics with Gravitational Waves, Cosmic Microwave
561 Background and Large-Scale Structure cross-correlations’’. SM is supported by
562 ERC Starting Grant No. 101163912–GravitySirens.

563 References

- 564 Abbott, B. P. et al. 2016, Phys. Rev. Lett., 116, 061102
565 Abbott, B. P. et al. 2017a, Phys. Rev. Lett., 119, 161101
566 Abbott, B. P. et al. 2017b, Astrophys. J. Lett., 848, L12
567 Abbott, B. P. et al. 2021a, Astrophys. J., 909, 218
568 Abbott, R. et al. 2021b, Astrophys. J. Lett., 913, L7
569 Abbott, R. et al. 2021c, Phys. Rev. D, 104, 022004
570 Abbott, R. et al. 2023a, Astrophys. J., 949, 76
571 Abbott, R. et al. 2023b, Phys. Rev. X, 13, 011048
572 Aghanim, N. et al. 2020, Astron. Astrophys., 641, A6, [Erratum: As-
573 tron.Astrophys. 652, C4 (2021)]
574 Artale, M. C., Bouffanais, Y., Mapelli, M., et al. 2020, Monthly Notices of the
575 RAS, 495, 1841
576 Auclair, P. et al. 2023, Living Rev. Rel., 26, 5
577 Behroozi, P. S., Wechsler, R. H., & Conroy, C. 2013, ApJ, 770, 57
578 Bellomo, N., Bertacca, D., Jenkins, A. C., et al. 2022, JCAP, 06, 030
579 Bera, S., Rana, D., More, S., & Bose, S. 2020, Astrophys. J., 902, 79
580 Borghi, N., Mancarella, M., Moresco, M., et al. 2024, Astrophys. J., 964, 191
581 Branchesi, M. et al. 2023, JCAP, 07, 068
582 Carretero, J., Castander, F. J., Gaztañaga, E., Crocce, M., & Fosalba, P. 2015,
583 Monthly Notices of the RAS, 447, 646

Fig. 7. The figure reports the PP Plots obtained taking each time a different line of sight when estimating the posterior, each from the 100 ones chosen covering a sky area of 10 deg^2 . The rows correspond to the three different thresholds in luminosity distance, the columns to different number of detected GW events N_{GW} .

584 Chassande-Mottin, E., Leyde, K., Mastrogiovanni, S., & Steer, D. A. 2019, *PhRvD*, 100, 083514
 585
 586 Chen, H.-Y., Fishbach, M., & Holz, D. E. 2018, *Nature*, 562, 545
 587 Chernoff, D. F. & Finn, L. S. 1993, *Astrophys. J. Lett.*, 411, L5
 588 Croce, M., Castander, F. J., Gaztañaga, E., Fosalba, P., & Carretero, J. 2015, *Monthly Notices of the RAS*, 453, 1513
 589
 590 Dalal, N., Holz, D. E., Hughes, S. A., & Jain, B. 2006, *Phys. Rev. D*, 74, 063006
 591 Del Pozzo, W. 2012, *Phys. Rev. D*, 86, 043011
 592 Essick, R. & Fishbach, M. 2024, *Astrophys. J.*, 962, 169
 593 Evans, M. et al. 2021 [arXiv: 2109.09882]
 594 Ezquiaga, J. M. & Holz, D. E. 2021, *Astrophys. J. Lett.*, 909, L23
 595 Ezquiaga, J. M. & Holz, D. E. 2022, *Phys. Rev. Lett.*, 129, 061102
 596 Farr, W. M. 2019, *Research Notes of the AAS*, 3, 66
 597 Finke, A., Foffa, S., Iacovelli, F., Maggiore, M., & Mancarella, M. 2021, *JCAP*, 08, 026
 598
 599 Fishbach, M., Holz, D. E., & Farr, W. M. 2018, *Astrophys. J. Lett.*, 863, L41
 600 Fishbach, M. et al. 2019, *Astrophys. J. Lett.*, 871, L13
 601 Fosalba, P., Croce, M., Gaztañaga, E., & Castander, F. J. 2015a, *Monthly Notices of the RAS*, 448, 2987
 602
 603 Fosalba, P., Gaztañaga, E., Castander, F. J., & Croce, M. 2015b, *Monthly Notices of the RAS*, 447, 1319
 604
 605 Gair, J. R., Ghosh, A., Gray, R., et al. 2023, *Astronomical Journal*, 166, 22
 606 Galbany, L. et al. 2023, *Astron. Astrophys.*, 679, A95
 607 Gerosa, D. & Moore, C. J. 2016, *PhRvL*, 117, 011101
 608 Gray, R., Beirnaert, F., Karathanasis, C., et al. 2023, *JCAP*, 2023, 023

Gray, R., Messenger, C., & Veitch, J. 2022, *Mon. Not. Roy. Astron. Soc.*, 512, 1127
 610
 611 Gray, R. et al. 2020, *Phys. Rev. D*, 101, 122001
 612 Hanselman, A. G., Vijaykumar, A., Fishbach, M., & Holz, D. E. 2025, *Astrophys. J.*, 979, 9
 613
 614 Hoffmann, K., Bel, J., Gaztañaga, E., et al. 2015, *Monthly Notices of the RAS*, 447, 1724
 615
 616 Holz, D. E. & Hughes, S. A. 2005, *Astrophys. J.*, 629, 15
 617 Kagra Collaboration, L. S. C. & VIRGO Collaboration. 2018, *Living Reviews in Relativity*, 21, 3
 618
 619 Karathanasis, C., Mukherjee, S., & Mastrogiovanni, S. 2023, *Mon. Not. Roy. Astron. Soc.*, 523, 4539
 620
 621 Leandro, H., Marra, V., & Sturani, R. 2022, *Phys. Rev. D*, 105, 023523
 622
 623 Leyde, K., Mastrogiovanni, S., Steer, D. A., Chassande-Mottin, E., & Karathanasis, C. 2022, *JCAP*, 09, 012
 624
 625 Madau, P. & Dickinson, M. 2014, *Annual Review of Astron and Astrophys*, 52, 415
 626
 627 Maggiore, M. et al. 2020, *JCAP*, 03, 050
 628
 629 Mandel, L., Farr, W. M., & Gair, J. R. 2019, *Mon. Not. Roy. Astron. Soc.*, 486, 1086
 630
 631 Mastrogiovanni, S., Laghi, D., Gray, R., et al. 2023, *Phys. Rev. D*, 108, 042002
 632 Mastrogiovanni, S., Leyde, K., Karathanasis, C., et al. 2021, *Phys. Rev. D*, 104, 062009
 633
 634 Mastrogiovanni, S., Pierra, G., Perriès, S., et al. 2024, *Astron. Astrophys.*, 682, A167
 635
 636 Mukherjee, S. 2022, *Mon. Not. Roy. Astron. Soc.*, 515, 5495

Lines - $\hat{d}_L^{\text{thr}} = 4250$ Mpc, area = 100 deg²

Fig. 8. Posterior obtained fixing H_0 to 70 km s⁻¹Mpc⁻¹, $\hat{d}_L^{\text{thr}} = 4250$ Mpc and the 500 detected GWs, for a sky area of 10 deg² and considering different lines of sight when reconstructing the posterior.

- 635 Mukherjee, S., Wandelt, B. D., Nisanke, S. M., & Silvestri, A. 2021, Phys. Rev.
636 D, 103, 043520
637 Mukherjee, S., Wandelt, B. D., & Silk, J. 2020, Mon. Not. Roy. Astron. Soc.,
638 494, 1956
639 Oguri, M. 2016, Phys. Rev. D, 93, 083511
640 Palmese, A., Bom, C. R., Mucesh, S., & Hartley, W. G. 2023, Astrophys. J., 943,
641 56
642 Palmese, A. et al. 2020, Astrophys. J. Lett., 900, L33
643 Sasaki, M., Suyama, T., Tanaka, T., & Yokoyama, S. 2018, CQGra, 35, 063001
644 Schutz, B. F. 1986, Nature, 323, 310
645 Sivia, D. & Skilling, J. 2006, Data analysis: a Bayesian tutorial (OUP Oxford)
646 Soares-Santos, M. et al. 2019, Astrophys. J. Lett., 876, L7
647 Taylor, S. R., Gair, J. R., & Mandel, I. 2012, Phys. Rev. D, 85, 023535
648 Vijaykumar, A., Fishbach, M., Adhikari, S., & Holz, D. E. 2024, Astrophys. J.,
649 972, 157
650 Vitale, S., Gerosa, D., Farr, W. M., & Taylor, S. R. 2020 [arXiv:2007.05579]
651 Wilk, M. B. & Gnanadesikan, R. 1968, Biometrika, 55, 1
652 Zonca, A., Singer, L., Lenz, D., et al. 2019, Journal of Open Source Software, 4,
653 1298

654 **Appendix A: Subsampling of the line-of-sights**

655 To ease the computational burden of the analyses, we subsam-
 656 ple the galaxies reported in every line-of-sight of MICEcat. We
 657 have found empirically that a subsampling of about ~ 3000
 658 galaxies does not modify the statistical properties of the galax-
 659 ies' distribution. We report in Fig. A.1 the comparison between
 660 the redshift (blue) and absolute magnitude (in orange) for the
 661 subsampled data with the full data (black) for the different sky
 662 areas we consider. We quantify the difference between the origi-
 663 nal and subsampled distributions using the discrete Kullback-
 664 Leibler (KL) divergence calculated by subdividing the redshift
 665 and magnitude ranges in 20 bins. We have found a KL diver-
 666 gence to be at most 10^{-1} . Hence we considered the subm-
 667 ples and the full distributions to be statistically indistinguish-
 668 able.

Fig. A.1. Comparison of the distribution of redshifts (left column) and magnitudes (right column) between original galaxies for some selected LOSs in MICEcat and the subsampled ones. The rows report sky areas respectively of 1 deg², 10 deg² and 100 deg².